

PHARMAAYURVED ONLINE RESEARCH JOURNAL FOR PHARMACY, AYURVED AND ALLIED SCIENCES

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POWDER MICROSCOPICAL EVALUATION - INGREDIENTS OF *SUGANDHI TRIPHALA*

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Article Received on: 04-06-24

Accepted on: 07-06-24

Published on: 15-06-24

Abstract

Background: *Churna* is defined in Ayurvedic medicine as a fine powder drug. *Churna* preparations are similar to the powder preparations of the allopathic system of medicine. In recent days, *churna* has been transformed into tablets for easily dose. These dosage forms are usually designed to improve the absorption of drugs due to the smaller particle size. Pharmacognosy is a simple and reliable tool to obtain complete information about a raw drug. Today, with the increased interest in phyto therapeutic agents, the availability of genuine plant material remains scarce. Determining the exact identity of the drugs is an integral part of this research. Most of the systems of traditional medicine are effective, but only need to be validated to assess the quality of the quantity and purity of the drugs. Hence standardization of Ayurvedic medicines is an important factor and basic needs of Ayurvedic medicine industry today. **Material & Method:** Powder microscopy of *Sugandhi Triphala* was carried out. *Sugandhi Triphala* is an ayurvedic formulation containing *Myristica fragrans* Houtt, *Syzygium aromaticum*, *Areca catechu* (Linn) Slides of each ingredient of *Sugandhi Triphala* were prepared using required reagents and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Sugandhi Triphala* starch grains, Endosperm, Fibre, Oil globules, parenchyma etc. **Discussion and Conclusion:** One of the simplest techniques for accurately identifying a herbal medicine is powder microscopy. It supports assurance and quality control for herbal medications. Furthermore, it helps standardize the new medication, preparing for commercial use.

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Key Words:

Powder microscopy, *Trigonella foenum gracecum* Linn., *Lapidium sativum* Linn., *Nigella sativa* Linn., *Trachyspermum ammi* Linn.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plant materials are categorized according to their microscopic, macro, and sensory characteristics. Assessing these characteristics is the first step in determining one's identity and purity of the plant materials used in medicine. It is recommended that these observations be carried out prior to conducting any additional observations. Medicinal plant materials are being frequently adulterated/substituted in common practice due to the number of regions such as similarity in morphological features, confusion in the regional name as written in classical text references, presence of inferior similar active principles in substituting plant materials, collector ignorance etc., resulted in less therapeutic activity of the finished dosage form.

Microscopy is a reliable method of the tool by which complete powder microscopic characters of the crude drugs can be obtained. Therefore, the detailed powdered microscopic study of the ingredients of *Sugandhi Triphala* has been carried out to establish its quality and purity of the powdered crude drug.

Here, for the present study *Sugandhi Trphala* is selected for the powder microscopy. *Trikarshika* is an important polyherbal formulation of the Ayurved mentioned in Raj Nighantu.¹ *Sugandhi Triphala* is an important polyherbal formulation of the Ayurved. It contains *Jatiphala* (*Myristica fragrans* Houtt), *Lavanga* (*Syzygium aromaticum* (Linn) Merril & Perry), *Pugaphala* (*Areca catechu* (Linn)).

AIM:

To analyse the microscopic features in the powder of *Sugandhi Triphala*.

OBJECTIVE:

To assess the microscopic features in the powder of *Jatiphala* (*Myristica fragrans* Houtt), *Lavanga* (*Syzygium aromaticum* (Linn) Merril & Perry), *Pugaphala* (*Areca catechu* (Linn)).

To compare the assessed features of herbal drugs with their standards mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Sugandhi Triphala was used for the powder microscopy. *Sugandhi Triphala* is an ayurvedic formulation containing *Jatiphala* (*Myristica fragrans* (Linn.) Maton), *Lavanga* (*Syzygium aromaticum* (Linn) Merril & Perry), *Pugaphala* (*Areca catechu* (Linn)) were collected and powdered following the standard operating procedure.

Slide preparation:

Slides of each ingredient of *Sugandhi Triphala* were prepared separately using required reagents and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in authentic reference.²⁻⁴

Staining agents: Safranin and iodine

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:**Table No.1: Powder microscopic characters found in *Sugandhi Triphala***

No.	Microscopic characters	<i>Jatiphala</i>	<i>Lavanga</i>	<i>Pugaphala</i>
1.	Elongated stone cells of testa	+		
2.	Starch grains	+		
3.	Endosperm with prism	+		+
4.	Crystalline masses of fat	+		
5.	Longitudinally cut fragments of xylem vessels & parenchyma		+	
6.	Fibre		+	+
7.	Fragment of stalk		+	
8.	Fragment of schizo- lysigenous oil glands in cross sectional view		+	
9.	Parenchyma cells of the hypanthium embedded with crystals		+	
10.	Fragments of anther lobe with stalk		+	
11.	Fragments of anther lobes		+	
12.	Pollen grains		+	
13.	Epidermis with overlapping subepidermis			+
14.	Transversely cut subepidermal sclereids			+
15.	Endosperm cells in surface view			+

Table No.2: Powder microscopic study of *Jatiphala* (*Myristica fragrans* Houtt)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Jatiphala</i>	Figure no.
1.	Elongated stone cells of testa	1.(a)
2.	Starch grains	1.(b)
3.	Prism	1.(c)
4.	Crystalline masses of fat	1.(e)

Table No.3: Powder microscopic study of *Lavanga* (*Syzygium aromaticum* (Linn) Merril & Perry)

No.	Characteristics of	Figure no.
1.	Longitudinally cut fragments of xylem vessels & parenchyma	2.(a)
2.	Fibre	2.(b)
3.	Fragment of stalk	2.(c)
4.	Fragment of schizo lgsigenous oil glands in cross sectional view	2.(e)
5.	Parenchyma cells of the hypanthium embedded with crystals	2.(f)
6.	Stalk of the anther lobe embedded with vascular strand oil cells and cluster crystal	2.(g)
7.	Pollen grain	2.(h)

Table No.4: Powder microscopic study of *Pugaphala* (*Areca catechu* (Linn))

No.	Characteristics of <i>Pugaphala</i>	Figure no.
1.	Epidermis with overlapping subepidermis	3.(a)
2.	Transversely cut subepidermal sclereids	3.(b)

3.	Endosperm cells in surface view	3.(c)
4.	Fibre	3.(d)

The current study provides knowledge on the microscopic characteristics of the herbal materials. The powder of *Sugandhi Triphala* was chosen for this microscopic investigation. Powder microscopy of *Jatiphala (Myristica fragrans* Houtt) shows, Elongated stone cells of testa, Starch grains, Endosperm, Crystalline masses of fat, Parenchyma cells with oil, Prismatic crystals of calcium oxalate. Powder microscopy of *Lavanga (Syzygium aromaticum* (Linn) Merril & Perry) shows, Longitudinally cut fragments of xylem vessels & parenchyma, Fibre, Fragment of stalk, Fragment of schizo-lysigenous oil glands in cross sectional view, Parenchyma cells of the hypanthium embedded with crystals, Longitudinally cut fragments of xylem vessels & parenchyma, , Fragments of anther lobe with stalk, Fragments of anther lobes, Fibrous layers in surface view. Powder microscopy of *Pugaphala (Areca catechu*(Linn) shows, Epidermis with overlapping subepidermis, Transversely cut subepidermal sclereids, Endosperm cells in surface view.

The process of standardizing Ayurvedic formulation is complex and difficult. However, it is imperative to ensure the effectiveness and safety of herbal remedies, making them appropriate for their application. In the current experiment, every powder component of *Sugandhi Triphala* was inspected under a microscope and its microscopic properties were noted. These qualities might be helpful in accurately recognizing and detecting impurities in goods that are sol

Powder microscopy study of Jatiphala

Powder microscopy of Lavanga

Longitudinally cut fragments of xylem vessels & parenchyma

Fig.2. (a)

Fibre

Fig.2. (b)

Fragment of stalk

Fig.2. (c)

Fragment of schizogen oil glands in cross sectional view

Fig.2. (d)

Parenchyma cells of the hypanthium embedded with crystals

Fig.2. (f)

Stalk of the anther lobe embedded with vascular strand oil cells and cluster crystal

Pollen grains

Fig.2. (g)

Fig.2. (h)

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Powder microscopy of Pugaphala

Epidermis with overlapping subepidermis

Fig.3. (a)

Transversely cut subepidermal sclereids

Fig.3. (b)

Endosperm cells in surface view

Fig.3. (c)

Fibre

Fig.3. (d)

CONCLUSION:

The current study's findings aid in the identification of herbal formulations like *Sugandhi triphala* as per this study an Ayurvedic formulation *Sugandhi Triphala* have structures like, Elongated stone cells of testa, Starch grains, Endosperm, Longitudinally cut fragments of xylem vessels & parenchyma, Fibre, Fragment of stalk, Oil globules, Epidermis with overlapping sub-epidermis, Transversely cut subepidermal sclereids, Endosperm cells in surface view.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The authors are thankful to Department of AYUSH, principal of Government Ayurved College, teachers and students of PG unit and Co-worker of GAC, Vadodara for their cordial support.

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